

Milestone: M5.1: Detailed planning of collaborations with research infrastructures in Europe and internationally

Lead Participant: ELIXIR Hub

Author: Andrea Guzmán Mesa & Joana Wingender

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Date Of Completion: 20/01/2025

Means of Verification

M5.1 Detailed planning of collaborations with research infrastructures in Europe and internationally (report)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No.

Project participants & others

Andrea Guzmán Mesa & Joana Wingender (Hub), Bengt Persson(SE), Patricia Palagi (CH), Silvio Tosatto (IT), Diana Battistella (IT), Ana Freitas (PT), Luciana Peixoto (PT), Bruna Piereckmoura (BE), Kim Gurwitz (EBI), Eva Alloza (ES).

Next action steps

Implementation of outlines steps in the milestone.

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